

PFUNS: Critical Experiments Benchmark

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803624

ABSTRACT

The PFUNS (Prompt Fission Uranium Neutron Spectrum) experiments were performed from January through March 2025 at the Department of Energy (DOE) National Criticality Research Center (NCERC). The main objective of the PFUNS experiments was to measure the prompt fission neutron spectrum of ^{235}U and to reduce its uncertainty above neutron energies of 8 MeV. To measure the prompt fission neutron spectrum, activation foils were placed in a central cavity of a critical experiment consisting of highly enriched uranium (HEU) metal hemi-shells, known as the Rocky Flats hemi-shells. The data from activation foils is being analyzed to unfold the prompt fission neutron spectrum. Four configurations that contained no activation foils were operated supercritical and are intended to be submitted to International Criticality Safety Benchmark Evaluation Project (ICSBEP) for further review and final approval. For each of the four configurations, uncertainties were evaluated in six categories: 1) critical measurement, 2) mass, 3) composition, 4) positioning, 5) dimensions, and 6) temperature. The largest contribution to each of the four configurations was due to the uncertainties in the dimensions of the HEU Rocky Flats shells. Preliminary Monte Carlo simulations using ENDF/B-VII.1 and ENDF/B-VIII.0 cross section are compared to experimental results. C-E values are also compared to other experiments that used similar sets of HEU hemi-shells.

Keywords: Critical experiments, HEU, Planet, PFUNS, NCERC

1. INTRODUCTION

The main purpose of the PFUNS experiments was to measure the prompt fission neutron spectrum of ^{235}U and reduce its uncertainty above neutron energies of 8 MeV. Activation foils were irradiated in the center cavity of a critical experiment consisting of HEU Rocky Flats hemi-shells [1]. The data from the activation is currently being analyzed to unfold the prompt fission neutron spectrum.

Four configurations containing no activation foils were selected with the intention of benchmarking these experiments and submitting their evaluations to the ICSBEP. The four configurations that were studied all consisted of Rocky Flats hemi-shells as the main fissile fuel. The Rocky Flats hemi-shells are a set of numbered nesting HEU hemi-shells that are routinely assembled in a variety of configurations. These HEU hemi-shells [2, 3, 4] have been used in other benchmark experiments which are documented in the ICSBEP Handbook. The four configurations that were assembled above delayed critical were intended to further address uncertainties in the ^{235}U neutron cross section data.

This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the four configurations and provides the experimental k_{eff} values. Section 3 discusses the evaluation of uncertainties for each configuration. The results of the Monte Carlo simulations are presented in section 4, along with some discussion of differences from an earlier evaluation. Finally, section 5 provides summary and conclusions.

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2. DESCRIPTION OF EXPERIMENTAL CONFIGURATIONS

Figure 1 shows a subset of the HEU hemi-shells used in the configurations, which have an average density of 18.6 g/cc. The first critical experiment contained 108.5 kg of uranium with no aluminum spacer between top and bottom parts of the stack. The second, third, and fourth critical experiments contained 114.0 kg of uranium with a 265, 275, and 285 mils aluminum spacer respectively between upper and lower parts of the stack. The aluminum spacers in the latter configurations were placed to limit the excess reactivity when the lower and upper parts of the stack were fully closed. Table I provides information regarding the Rocky Flats hemi-shells and aluminum spacer used in each of the four critical experiments.

Figure 1. Rocky Flats hemi-shells.

Table I. Rocky Flats hemi-shells and spacer rings used in each of the four critical configurations.

Configuration	Rocky Flats Shells	HEU Mass	Spacer Ring Total Gap
1	33, 35-63	108.5 kg	-
2	33, 35-64	114.0 kg	0.6731 cm
3	33, 35-64	114.0 kg	0.6985 cm
4	33, 35-64	114.0 kg	0.7239 cm

Figure 2 shows the lower stack of the second configuration on the movable platen of the Planet vertical assembly machine with a 265-mil aluminum spacer. The upper stack sits on a membrane and is seen in Figure 3.

2.1. Rocky Flats hemi-shells

The Rocky Flats shells are nesting hemi-shells of HEU. They were fabricated in 1965 for the Rocky Flats Critical Mass Laboratory [5]. Each hemi-shell is approximately 0.33 cm thick. The hemi-shells are numbered as “odd” and “even” set such that “odd” hemi-shells nest within each other and “even” hemi-shells do as well. The dimensions and weights of hemi-shells are given in Table II. The dimensions in Table II are from reference [5] and the weights were obtained in 2024 prior to performing the experiments and after the experiments were completed. Note that hemi-shell #34 is not used in any of the experiments. The average of the mass between the two measurements was used to calculate the density of the hemi-shells and used as an input in the MCNP simulations that follow.

Table III shows the isotopic composition of the Rocky Flats hemi-shells given in reference [5]. There were two measurements reported in reference [5]. Again, the average of these two measurements was used as an input in the MCNP simulations that will follow.

Figure 2. Bottom part of the stack showing the 265-mil aluminum spacer.

Figure 3. Top portion of the PFUNS experiments.
Table II. Dimensions and masses of Rocky Flats hemi-shells.

Shell #	Inner Radius (cm)	Outer Radius (cm)	Mass (g) before	Mass (g) after	Shell #	Inner Radius (cm)	Outer Radius (cm)	Mass (g) before	Mass (g) after
33	7.0060	7.3296	1933.6	1933.4	34	7.0098	7.3338	1934.3	-
35	7.3417	7.6658	2119.5	2119.6	36	7.3428	7.6665	2118.3	2117.8
37	7.6824	8.0027	2334.0	2334.1	38	7.6711	8.0027	2329.0	2329.0
39	8.0128	8.3364	2513.4	2513.2	40	8.0075	8.3292	2495.3	2495.3
41	8.3462	8.6683	2707.3	2707.2	42	8.3443	8.6680	2725.3	2725.6
43	8.6782	8.9996	2928.0	2928.2	44	8.6764	8.9995	2934.9	2934.9
45	9.0095	9.3328	3169.3	3169.1	46	9.0104	9.3329	3158.7	3158.5
47	9.3418	9.6667	3421.1	3421.0	48	9.3432	9.6683	3427.0	3427.0
49	9.6771	9.9999	3635.6	3635.3	50	9.6775	10.0001	3634.6	3634.6
51	10.0119	10.3340	3895.4	3894.9	52	10.0104	10.3336	3900.8	3900.4
53	10.3445	10.6696	4189.1	4188.8	54	10.3427	10.6685	4187.3	4187.1
55	10.6743	11.0009	4450.5	4450.2	56	10.6773	11.0013	4445.5	4445.1
57	11.0113	11.3348	4726.9	4727.0	58	11.0112	11.3315	4724.1	4723.4
59	11.3439	11.6660	4996.8	4996.8	60	11.3444	11.6670	5023.4	5023.0
61	11.6765	11.9987	5321.6	5320.9	62	11.6785	12.0015	5324.7	5325.0
63	12.0108	12.3358	5656.8	5655.9	64	12.0111	12.3363	5624.9	5624.7

Table III. Isotopic composition of Rocky Flats hemi-shells.

Isotope	1965 Mass Fraction [%]	1971 Mass Fraction [%]
²³³ U	Not recorded	Not recorded
²³⁴ U	1.00	1.02
²³⁵ U	93.19	93.16
²³⁶ U	0.40	0.47
²³⁸ U	5.41	5.35

2.2. Miscellaneous components

Other components such as containment shells, support shell, center support bar, membrane, etc., are shown in Figure 4. These components are described in detail in reference [6] and [7] and were part of the detailed MCNP model used in the uncertainty analyses simulations described in section 3.

2.3. Experimental k_{eff}

Four configurations described in section 2 were operated above delayed critical. The reactivity of the experiments was calculated using the Inhour equation [1], where ρ is the reactivity in dollars, Δ is the prompt neutron lifetime of the configuration given in seconds, β_{eff}/Λ is the measured Rossi- α at delayed critical in (seconds)⁻¹. For these configurations, the Rossi- α is $1.1 \times 10^6 \text{ sec}^{-1}$, which is the Rossi- α for Lady Godiva [8]. T is the measured reactor period in seconds. β_{eff} is the delayed neutron fraction, 0.0065. β_i/β_{eff} is the relative abundance of precursor group i and λ_i is the decay constant of precursor group i . Reference [9] lists the delayed neutron parameters used in Eq. 1 for a fast ²³⁵U system.

Figure 4. Exploded view of the PFUNS experiments.

$$\rho(\$) = \frac{\Lambda}{T\beta_{eff}} + \sum_{i=1}^6 \frac{(\frac{\beta_i}{\beta_{eff}})}{1+\lambda_i T} \quad (1)$$

Based on Eq.1, the calculated reactivity and associated standard deviation obtained for each configuration is shown in Table IV. The exponential rise in the neutron population was measured with three ion chambers located around the Planet vertical assembly machine. Fitting the exponential rise yielded the reactor period also reported in Table IV. The uncertainty reported in Table IV for the reactor period is the standard deviation based on hundreds of individual fits of the ion chamber data using the Levenberg-Marquard least square fitting technique. It is important to note that standard deviation found is greater than the uncertainty of a single fit [10]. As for the uncertainty in the β_{eff} , the value of β_{eff} used to calculate the k_{eff} s in Table IV is 0.0065. To assess any potential uncertainty in the delayed

neutron parameters, the β_{eff} value is modified by a conservatively high 15% up to 0.0074. This serves as a bounding value to prove that the selection of a value for β_{eff} does not contribute meaningfully to the overall experimental uncertainty.

Table IV Reactivity measurement of critical configurations.

Configuration	Reactor period (s)	Reactivity (cents)	k_{eff}
1 (no spacer)	112.58 ± 0.38	8.68 ± 0.02	$1.00056 \pm <0.00001$
	113.73 ± 0.30	8.61 ± 0.02	$1.00056 \pm <0.00001$
	113.43 ± 0.38	8.63 ± 0.02	$1.00056 \pm <0.00001$
Average	113.33 ± 0.21	8.63 ± 0.01	$1.00056 \pm <0.00001$
2 (265 mil spacer)	15.09 ± 0.12	31.94 ± 0.12	$1.00208 \pm <0.00001$
	15.16 ± 0.10	31.87 ± 0.10	$1.00208 \pm <0.00001$
	15.11 ± 0.12	31.92 ± 0.12	$1.00208 \pm <0.00001$
Average	15.12 ± 0.06	31.90 ± 0.07	$1.00208 \pm <0.00001$
3 (275 mil spacer)	37.25 ± 0.30	19.18 ± 0.10	$1.00125 \pm <0.00001$
	37.32 ± 0.19	19.16 ± 0.06	$1.00125 \pm <0.00001$
	37.34 ± 0.19	19.15 ± 0.06	$1.00125 \pm <0.00001$
Average	37.31 ± 0.12	19.16 ± 0.04	$1.00125 \pm <0.00001$
4 (285 mil spacer)	132.62 ± 0.55	7.60 ± 0.03	$1.00049 \pm <0.00001$
	133.67 ± 0.41	7.55 ± 0.02	$1.00049 \pm <0.00001$
	133.58 ± 0.45	7.56 ± 0.02	$1.00049 \pm <0.00001$
Average	133.39 ± 0.26	7.57 ± 0.01	$1.00049 \pm <0.00001$

3. EVALUATION OF UNCERTAINTIES

The sensitivity and uncertainty effects for the four configurations examined were evaluated using Monte Carlo N-Particle®¹ Version 6.3.0 and ENDF/B-VIII.0 neutron cross section libraries [11]. The MCNP simulations were completed using 1,000,000 histories per generation with 5000 active generations. The statistical 1σ uncertainty associated with all Monte Carlo calculations is ± 0.00001 or ± 1 pcm.

The first category, critical measurement, explains how the reactivity of each of the two configurations was evaluated. The uncertainties included here are the reactor period measurement and the delayed neutron fraction discussed in section 2.3.

The second category, mass, evaluated uncertainties with the adjoint-based relative sensitivity coefficients (KSEN capability in MCNP [12]) using Eqs. 2 and 3. u_i is the uncertainty of the parameter being perturbed, in this case the uncertainty in the mass of each component that is part or close to the experiment. δx_i is the size of the mass perturbation. $S_{k,i}$ is the relative sensitivity of k_{eff} with respect to x_i . The derivatives computed and used are constant-volume partial derivatives. The mass uncertainty of every component is analyzed, including the Rocky Flats shells, other core components, and the structural components around the assembly.

$$u_{k,i} = \pm u_i \frac{\delta k_{eff}}{\delta x_i} \quad (2)$$

$$u_{k,i} = \pm \frac{u_i}{x_{i,0}} k_{eff,0} S_{k,i} \quad (3)$$

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The third category, composition, looks at the uncertainty in the material composition (e.g. isotopics and impurities) for each component. Like the mass uncertainties, these were also calculated using the adjoint-based approaches of Eq. 2 and 3 and the MCNP KSEN card.

The fourth category, positioning, analyzes uncertainties in where each component in the assembly was located. Examples of this include possible errors in the location of the Rocky Flats shells, the membrane, and other components around the assembly.

The fifth category, geometry, evaluated uncertainties in the dimensions of the components. For these calculations, direct perturbations were performed where the mass was held constant. Each dimension for every component is analyzed individually, and similar components were varied simultaneously.

Finally, the uncertainty in the temperature of the material and its surroundings was analyzed.

Table V shows the uncertainties associated with each category for each configuration. As expected, the uncertainty associated with the dimensions of the Rocky Flats hemi-shells was the largest of all the categories in each of the configurations. Finally, the total uncertainty for these experiments shown in Table V compares quite well with the total uncertainty for Lady Godiva of ± 100 pcm given in reference [13].

Table V Uncertainties for each of the configurations.

Category	Configuration #1	Configuration #2	Configuration #3	Configuration #4
Critical Measurement	± 13 pcm	± 20 pcm	± 27 pcm	± 28 pcm
Mass	± 10 pcm	± 10 pcm	± 10 pcm	± 10 pcm
Composition	± 15 pcm	± 16 pcm	± 16 pcm	± 16 pcm
Positioning	± 22 pcm	± 22 pcm	± 22 pcm	± 21 pcm
Dimensions	± 63 pcm	± 111 pcm	± 107 pcm	± 107 pcm
Temperature	± 8 pcm	± 8 pcm	± 9 pcm	± 9 pcm
Total	± 71 pcm	± 117 pcm	± 114 pcm	± 115 pcm

4. RESULTS OF MCNP SIMULATIONS

Preliminary MCNP results are shown in Table VI as well as the experimental k_{eff} . As seen in Table VI, the ENDF/B-VIII.0 (C-E) values are in similar agreement with the experimental k_{eff} as the C-E ENDF/B-VIII.1 results[14]. These results agree quite well with the trend of those published in the MUSIC (Measurements of Uranium Subcritical and Critical) benchmark experiments [4]; however, the C-E values in Table VI are a bit larger than those in reference [4], which were less than 100 pcm.

Table VI MCNP preliminary results.

Config.	Experimental k_{eff}	ENDF/B-VIII.0	C-E (pcm)	ENDF/B-VIII.1	C-E (pcm)
1	$1.00056 \pm <0.00001$	0.99651 ± 0.00001	-405	0.99636 ± 0.00001	-420
2	$1.00208 \pm <0.00001$	0.99896 ± 0.00001	-378	0.99882 ± 0.00001	-326
3	$1.00125 \pm <0.00001$	0.99830 ± 0.00001	-295	0.99818 ± 0.00001	-307
4	$1.00049 \pm <0.00001$	0.99748 ± 0.00001	-301	0.99732 ± 0.00001	-317

One possible reason for this larger difference is due to the larger hemishells used in the PFUNS experiment. It is possible that this is causing the system to be sensitive to different parts of the nuclear data, such as elastic or inelastic scattering, more than the MUSiC experiments. This can be seen when comparing the plots of cross section sensitivity shown in Figure 5. This could hint at potential improvements being necessary in the scattering nuclear data for ^{235}U . One additional note is that the simplification effects related to removing components from the model were larger in PFUNS than in MUSiC. For example, removing the concrete and crane in the room from the model changed k_{eff} by 77 pcm in PFUNS, while the effect in MUSiC was 63 pcm. Again, this is likely due to the larger radius shells being more affected by the reflection back into the room.

Figure 5. A Comparison of Elastic and Inelastic Scattering Sensitivities for the MUSIC and PFUNS experiments.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Four bare HEU critical experiments with no activation foils were performed with the intention to benchmark these experiments and to submit their evaluations to the ICSBEP. For each of the four experiments, the uncertainty associated with the dimensions of the HEU hemi-shells was the largest when compared to the other five categories (critical measurement, mass, composition, positioning, and temperature). MCNP simulations were performed using ENDF/B-VIII.0 and ENDF/B-VII.1 neutron cross section libraries. In all four cases, simulations using ENDF/B-VIII.0 performed very similarly to ENDF/B-VII.1. The modeling of the PFUNS experiments included more external components because of the larger surface area of the Rocky Flats hemi-shells compared to other experiments that have used smaller dimensions HEU hemi-shells. Finally, sensitivities of the elastic and inelastic scattering cross sections for ^{235}U suggested that an improvement to these cross sections may be necessary to reduce the C-E values.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The work presented in this paper was supported by the Department of Energy (DOE) Nuclear Criticality Safety Program (NCSP), funded and managed by the National Nuclear Security Administration (NNSA) for DOE. The authors would like to thank Nicholas Wynne and his team for providing the mechanical engineering support needed for safe operation of these experiments, along with Jesson Hutchinson for internal review of the evaluation, and Jeremy Bez of Autorité de Sûreté Nucléaire et de Radioprotection for the external review. Additionally, NCERC Facility Operations and Mission Support and Test Services staff assisted with experiment execution.

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